

MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article discusses various ways of using modern educational technologies in teaching Russian as a native language at school.

Keywords: russian language, technical means of teaching, requirements, educational information, learning process, lesson.

In the era of globalization and rapid scientific and technological progress, children perceive information differently than it was twenty or thirty years ago. This fact must be taken into account when teaching students. A feature of learning at the present stage is the need to use game technologies, non-standard approaches and techniques in order to keep children's attention, better assimilation of the material and increase motivation for further study of a certain subject, which undoubtedly affects the overall learning outetechnical means of teaching me.

To implement the above tasks, information and communication technologies have proved to be the most effective today, and the use of technical training tools has become a prerequisite for any lesson. Learning tools are various objects used by the teacher and students in the learning process.

In modern pedagogy, technical means of teaching (technical means of teaching) are the most developed and promising means. With the help of a variety of technical means of teaching , educational information is presented to the student and its assimilation is controlled [2]. Educational information can be presented on multimedia slides, in movies, on simulation stands, simulators, etc. Each of these tools is an independent source of information and visual learning. Today, all technical means of teaching are differentiated by functional purpose into 3 groups: informational, controlling, teaching,

Regardless of the type of technical means of teaching , they are subject to various requirements: functional, pedagogical, ergonomic, aesthetic, economic, etc. [1] Functional requirements indicate that technical means of teaching must provide the necessary operating modes: volume, sound quality, reproduction, etc. Pedagogical requirements — requirements for the compliance of the capabilities of the technical means of teaching with the form and methods of the educational process consistent with the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard. Ergonomic requirements are focused on the safety of

operation, convenience and ease of operation, noise level, etc. Aesthetic requirements speak of the need for harmony of form, size, proportionality, integrity of the composition. Economic requirements are reduced to a relatively low cost with high quality and durability of technical means of teaching . With the combination of the above requirements for technical means of teaching , educational organizations will be able to equip more classes with them and expand the range of application of these tools in many subjects.

Unlike conventional technical means of teaching, ICTs allow not only to saturate the student with a large amount of ready-made, strictly selected, appropriately organized knowledge, but also to develop the intellectual creative abilities of students, their ability to independently acquire new knowledge, work with various sources of information. One of the advantages of using multimedia technology in teaching is to improve the quality of training due to the novelty of the activity, interest in working with a computer. The use of a computer in Russian language and literature lessons can become a new method of organizing active and meaningful work of students, making it more visual and interesting.

The use of ICT in Russian language and literature lessons will improve the quality of teaching the subject; reflect the essential aspects of philological objects, visibly implementing the principle of visibility; to bring to the fore the most important (in terms of educational goals and objectives) characteristics of the studied objects In Russian language lessons, information resources are used at all stages of learning: - when presenting new material: visualization of knowledge (demonstration and encyclopedic programs, presentation programs, interactive whiteboard); — at the stage of consolidating the studied material (simulator programs); - when students work independently (tutoring programs, electronic encyclopedias, educational programs); — for individual training of specific abilities of the student: attention, memory, thinking, etc— - during the control and verification of the studied (programs for testing and control) [2].

The use of ICT in Russian language lessons allows you to diversify the forms of work, the activities of students, to activate attention, to increase the creative potential of the individual, motivation for successful study of educational material, to use to diversify illustrative and informational material [3]. Due to the fact that the material is presented in an interactive mode, the communicative interaction with students is significantly improved, which makes it possible to bring information to them faster and more efficiently. Accordingly, the quality of education is also improving. The motivation and involvement of students in the classroom increases. Unlike printed ones, spreadsheets have

increased visibility. The same table can be used throughout the entire period of studying any topic, since tables are multilevel, containing complete information on any section (for example, "Pronouns" or "Noun"). In the work, you can use ready-made software products (methodological complex, "Encyclopedia of Russian Literature", "The Great Encyclopedia of Cyril and Methodius", etc.). Virtual school disks contain theoretical and practical material, questions for fixing, tasks for the lesson, simulators, texts. It should be noted the depth of the analysis of the works, the variety of the material, the brightness of the presentation. The teacher can use this material at his discretion, having carefully studied and selected what is necessary. Electronic dictionaries and encyclopedias allow you to get additional knowledge mobile and use them in the lesson. Interactive whiteboards are a set of equipment that makes it possible to make the learning process vivid, visual and dynamic. It allows you to cover a large amount of material, organize inspections, make corrections and adjustments, make comments, saving materials for further correction.

Thus, the use of modern technical means of teaching in the lessons of the Russian language allows us to solve one of the most important tasks of learning - the activation of cognitive activity. In addition, such training involves all the main sensory systems of a person, increases motivation for learning, and makes it possible to individualize learning.

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